

HIGH STRAIN RATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A TOROSPHERICAL SHELL COMPOSED OF IM7/E7T1-2 GRAPHITE EPOXY COMPOSITE

Alexander T. Dee¹, Jack R. Vinson¹ and George Leon²

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware.*

² *Electric Boat Division, General Dynamics, Groton, Connecticut.*

SUMMARY: Polymer matrix composites offer excellent mechanical properties such as high specific strength and stiffness, making them attractive for applications in several naval, aerospace, automotive, and recreational-sports structural components. Although many composite materials are selected for applications where high strain rate loading is probable, little is known of their responses to shock loading. Mechanical properties can vary significantly with strain rate. Therefore, the use of static properties in the analysis and design of structures which undergo dynamic loading may unfortunately lead to very conservative, overweight designs or lead to designs which fail prematurely and unexpectedly. The use of dynamic material properties ensures that designs are optimized for structural integrity and weight efficiency when subjected to dynamic loading.

In this study, a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar is used to obtain high-strain-rate, compressive mechanical properties of a 48 inch diameter, quasi-isotropic, torospherical shell composed of IM7/E7T1-2 graphite epoxy composite. The shell is part of an external, pressure-proof storage module which is attached to a submersible vehicle and designed to support equipment internally at atmospheric pressure. In combat situations, this structure may be exposed to underwater explosions, therefore warranting the need for dynamic material properties. For in-plane and out-of-plane directions, the yield strength, yield strain, ultimate strength, ultimate strain, and modulus of elasticity are presented for strain rates varying from 381 sec⁻¹ to 1154 sec⁻¹. The data from the 49 dynamic tests are statistically analyzed, represented by equations, compared to quasi-static material properties, and discussed in some detail.

KEYWORDS: high-strain-rate, IM7/E7T1-2, Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar.

INTRODUCTION

The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar facility at the University of Delaware is described Ref. 1. Impact is initiated by releasing nitrogen gas from a pressurized chamber which causes the specimen to be compressed between the two bars. The striker bar is displaced on Teflon rings through the barrel where it strikes the incident bar (bar 1). The velocity of the striker bar, V_{sb} , just prior to impact is measured using two infrared beams set four inches apart.

Upon impact with the striker bar, the incident bar receives an elastic compressive strain wave with a wave velocity C_B and a wave shape $\epsilon_1(t)$ and is displaced along its length axis. This bar is guided by Teflon bearings which are bolted to a steel I-beam and secured on a reinforced concrete base to minimize any vibration. When the wave reaches the bar 1-specimen interface, a portion of the incident wave is reflected back into bar 1 as a tensile wave with a

wave shape $\epsilon_R(t)$. The remaining portion is transmitted into the specimen as a compressive wave. The wave transmitted into the specimen travels through the specimen and reaches the specimen-bar 2 interface, where a portion of the wave is reflected back into the specimen. The remaining portion is transmitted into bar 2 as a compressive wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_T(t)$. Bar 2 is displaced similarly to bar 1, but is arrested after the test by a simple dash pot.

Because the specimen length is short compared to the bar lengths, the initial stress wave in the specimen undergoes numerous internal reflections during the test. It is calculated that the initial wave duration in a typical specimen is approximately two microseconds. Within a composite material specimen, there may be differences in the wave speed in the fiber and matrix materials. However, if a minimum of four wave reflections within the specimen is achieved prior to specimen failure, the stress distribution along the specimen length is smoothed out and the specimen is assumed to be in a uniform state of stress at any instant [2,3]. At the University of Delaware SHPB, the wave pulse time window (defined as the time it takes a wave to travel the length of the striker bar and back) is approximately 290 microseconds. Thus, to record information accurately at specimen failure, the specimen must fail within 290 microseconds after the start of the test and also after a time such that four internal reflections in the specimen has been achieved.

Strain gages are mounted on bars 1 and 2 equidistant from the specimen interfaces and are connected to an oscilloscope. The oscilloscope records and stores the output from the strain gages. Using this data, the stress and strain versus time of the specimen during the test can be calculated for the strain rate of that particular test.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

The shell is made of IM7/E7T1-2 (rubber toughened) with the following quasi-isotropic lay-up: $[45/135/90_2/45/135/0_2/45/135/90_5[45/135/0_8/45/135/90_8]_545/135/0_5/45/135]_s$. A section of the torospherical shell was provided by the Electric Boat Division of General Dynamics.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Compression specimens in the shape of right circular cylinders (1/4 inches in diameter and 3/8 inches in length) were machined from the shell and prepared for testing by the senior author. Care was taken to machine samples which displayed minimal visible effects of the inherent shell curvature. However, the effects of the curvature are expected to give some variation in the results. Another source of error is due to the stacking sequence coupled with the small diameter of each test sample. Since core drilling was done at random locations in the through-thickness, specimens are expected to have slightly different stacking sequences.

TEST RESULTS

Since the laminate lay-up is such that the shell is quasi-isotropic, the 1-direction refers to any in-plane direction, while the 3-direction denotes the through-thickness direction perpendicular to the fibers. For completeness, all the data from the 24 tests in the 1-direction and the 25 tests in the 3-direction are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Quasi-static tests were performed on an Instron universal machine at a strain rate of 0.05 inches/second. Quasi-static strength data for the shell material is provided in Table 5. These data will allow other researchers to study and analyze the tests independently. These data are then presented statistically in Tables 3, 4, and 6 which provide mean values and standard deviations.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS, RESULTS, AND DISCUSSION

It is interesting to see that with the complexities of these high strain rate tests, and the small sample sizes, how small the coefficient of variance (COV), (i.e. the ratio of standard deviation to mean value, given as a percentage), is for the various mechanical properties as shown in Table 7. The highest COV value is 35.8% (on a modulus of elasticity) while the lowest COV is 2.1% (on a yield strength).

To analyze the trends from Tables 3, 4, and 6, it is important to define significant differences. For the present purpose, a quantity P is said to be significantly different from Q if the mean value of P falls outside the region of the mean ± 3 standard deviations of Q. The ± 3 standard deviations are plotted as error bars for each relevant dynamic material property in Figures 1-5 as a visual means of determining significant differences.

From Table 3, it is seen that there is little significant difference in the range of strain rates for the 1-direction. Only the strain rates of groups D and E are significantly different from the group A strain rate. Failure of the specimens was achieved at each strain rate. Yielding was not found in the 1-direction except at the low strain rate. Therefore, in the strain rate range between 381.1 sec^{-1} and 457.1 sec^{-1} , a transition from ductile to brittle behavior must occur. This trend from ductile behavior to brittle behavior has been noticed in other polymer matrix composite materials. Concerning ultimate strength, Figure 1 shows that these values do not differ significantly with strain rate. Ultimate strain values show that group D is significantly different to group C, and that group E is significantly different to groups B and C (Figure 2). Modulus of elasticity values show little dependence on strain rate. Only the group A modulus of elasticity is significantly different from the other groups (Figure 5).

From Table 4, strain rates in the 3-direction are generally significantly different except that groups F, G, H, and J are not significantly different from group I, and Group I is not significantly different from group J. Yielding was found in the 3-direction for all strain rates, and yield strength values show an increasing trend with strain rate. Yield strength values of groups F and G are significantly different from the other groups with the exception of group H, and groups H and J are only significantly different from group F. Group I is only significantly different from groups F and J (Figure 3b). Yield strain values show an increasing trend with strain rate but have little significant difference among the groups. Only the yield strain of group F is significantly different from the other groups (Figure 4). Ultimate strength, ultimate strain, and modulus of elasticity all show no strain rate dependence (Figures 3a, 4, and 5, respectively).

It is seen that significant differences are prevalent when comparing dynamic material properties to the quasi-static material properties in Table 6. The quasi-static ultimate strength value in the 1-direction is significantly different only from groups C and E. However, the ultimate strength value of groups A-E are all significantly different from the quasi-static value. For the 3-direction, the ultimate strength quasi-static value shows a significant difference only to group F. However, the ultimate strength value of groups F-J are all significantly different from the quasi-static value. Yielding was not present in quasi-static tests for either the 1 nor the 3-direction.

FRACTOGRAPHY

Figure 6 shows a scanning electron microscope (SEM) photo of a 1-direction fracture surface tested at 527 sec^{-1} . The photo shows interfacial debonding, resin cusps associated with brittle fracture in resin rich areas [4], and resin cracks. Figure 7 shows an SEM photo of a 3-direction fracture surface tested at 245 sec^{-1} . The photo shows interfacial debonding and fiber fracture near a large crack.

CONCLUSIONS

The data from these 49 experiments for the IM7/E7T1-2 torospherical shell in the in-plane and through-thickness directions provides a data bank for this material at room temperature for strain rates between 381 sec^{-1} to 1154 sec^{-1} . Yielding in the 1-direction occurs only at the low strain rate. Thus, there is a transition from a ductile to a brittle behavior between strain rates of 381 sec^{-1} and 457 sec^{-1} . Yielding is present in the 3-direction for all strain rates, with yield strength increasing 2.13 times and yield strain increasing 4.97 times between strain rates of 382 sec^{-1} and 1154 sec^{-1} .

The ultimate strength in the 1-direction is strain rate insensitive. Ultimate strain and modulus of elasticity are nearly strain rate insensitive, with only the group A ultimate strain and modulus of elasticity being significantly different from the other groups. In the 3-direction, the ultimate strength, ultimate strain, and modulus of elasticity are strain rate insensitive.

There are significant differences between dynamic and quasi-static compressive material properties. In the 1-direction, the quasi-static ultimate strength is lower than all dynamic ultimate strengths. The quasi-static ultimate strength in the 1-direction is 29.4% lower than the highest, dynamic ultimate strength reported. In the 3-direction, the quasi-static ultimate strength is higher than its dynamic counterpart, being 28.3% higher than the lowest dynamic ultimate strength.

Yielding was not observed in quasi-static compression tests. Since yielding is seen in the 1-direction only at the lowest strain rate of 381 sec^{-1} , the 1-direction appears to display a second transitional behavior: the first being the transition from ductile to brittle behavior discussed earlier, and the second being a transition from brittle to ductile behavior between quasi-static loading and the 381 sec^{-1} strain rate. Since yielding is seen in all the 3-direction dynamic tests, a transition from brittle to ductile behavior must exist between quasi-static loading and the 382 sec^{-1} strain rate. More experiments may provide greater detail for all of the above conclusions.

Fig. 1: Ultimate and Yield Strength as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2, 1-direction

Fig. 2: Ultimate and Yield Strain as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2, 1-Direction

Fig. 3a: Ultimate Strength as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2, 3-Direction

Fig. 3b: Yield Strength as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2, 3-Direction

Fig. 4: Ultimate and Yield Strain as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2, 3-Direction

Fig. 5: Modulus of Elasticity as a Function of Strain Rate: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2

Fig. 6: SEM photo of a 1-direction specimen failure surface tested at 527 sec^{-1} , showing interfacial debonding, resin cracks, and cusps

Fig. 7: SEM Photo of a 3-Direction Specimen Failure Surface Tested at 245 sec^{-1} , showing fiber failure and interfacial debonding near a crack

Table 1: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: 1-Direction Tests

Group	Pressure (psi)	Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Strength (psi)	Ult Strength (psi)	Yield Strain (%)	Ult Strain (%)	Modulus (psi)	Notes
A1	20	349	6.52E+04	8.50E+04	0.63%	1.26%	1.04E+07	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction. Fracture between plies adjacent to the woven ply visible.
A2	20	387	6.30E+04	7.11E+04	0.60%	1.20%	1.06E+07	
A3	20	434	5.70E+04	5.97E+04	0.71%	1.61%	8.06E+06	
A4	20	351	6.18E+04	8.06E+04	0.65%	1.19%	9.49E+06	
A5	20	384	-	9.68E+04	-	0.81%	1.20E+07	
B1	40	527	-	7.62E+04	-	1.10%	6.93E+06	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction. Fracture between plies adjacent to the woven ply visible.
B2	40	514	-	6.46E+04	-	1.10%	5.88E+06	
B3	40	370	-	8.54E+04	-	1.17%	7.30E+06	
B4	40	481	-	7.16E+04	-	1.20%	5.97E+06	
B5	40	393	-	7.35E+04	-	1.14%	6.45E+06	
C1	60	433	-	9.35E+04	-	1.13%	8.27E+06	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction. Fracture between plies adjacent to the woven ply visible. Many splinters.
C2	60	520	-	7.78E+04	-	1.17%	6.65E+06	
C3	60	490	-	7.62E+04	-	1.19%	6.41E+06	
C4	60	406	-	8.59E+04	-	1.15%	7.47E+06	
D1	80	468	-	9.41E+04	-	1.24%	7.59E+06	Fracture mostly in the fiber direction. Fracture between plies adjacent to woven ply visible. Many splintered fragments.
D2	80	666	-	7.57E+04	-	1.28%	5.90E+06	
D3	80	420	-	6.56E+04	-	1.11%	5.91E+06	
D4	80	619	-	8.32E+04	-	1.31%	6.35E+06	
D5	80	611	-	8.27E+04	-	1.30%	6.36E+06	
E1	100	465	-	7.41E+04	-	1.27%	6.00E+06	Fracture mostly in the fiber direction. Fracture between plies adjacent to woven ply visible. Many splintered fragments.
E2	100	712	-	7.35E+04	-	1.65%	4.46E+06	
E3	100	573	-	8.32E+04	-	1.42%	5.86E+06	
E4	100	552	-	8.16E+04	-	1.41%	5.79E+06	
E5	100	515	-	8.79E+04	-	1.28%	6.87E+06	

Table 2: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: 3-Direction Tests

Group	Pressure (psi)	Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Strength (psi)	Ult Strength (psi)	Yield Strain (%)	Ult Strain (%)	Modulus (psi)	Notes
F1	20	320	-	7.41E+04	-	4.95%	1.50E+06	Fracture predominately at one end of specimen. 50-75% of specimen intact.
F2	20	339	-	7.73E+04	-	6.54%	1.18E+06	
F3	20	398	2.27E+04	8.19E+04	0.83%	5.33%	2.72E+06	
F4	20	477	2.18E+04	7.34E+04	0.96%	4.96%	2.28E+06	
F5	20	376	-	7.11E+04	-	5.03%	1.41E+06	
G1	40	693	4.98E+04	7.78E+04	1.38%	4.57%	3.62E+06	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction.
G2	40	698	2.95E+04	6.50E+04	1.11%	4.54%	2.66E+06	
G3	40	640	3.16E+04	8.01E+04	1.17%	5.37%	2.69E+06	
G4	40	666	4.94E+04	7.71E+04	1.41%	4.47%	3.50E+06	
G5	40	713	2.67E+04	5.75E+04	1.25%	4.56%	2.15E+06	
H1	60	860	4.35E+04	8.43E+04	1.55%	5.33%	2.81E+06	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction. Many splinters.
H2	60	873	3.82E+04	8.47E+04	1.37%	4.98%	2.78E+06	
H3	60	839	4.75E+04	8.45E+04	1.51%	5.12%	3.15E+06	
H4	60	857	5.63E+04	7.58E+04	1.62%	4.55%	3.46E+06	
H5	60	846	3.77E+04	7.42E+04	1.76%	5.58%	2.15E+06	
I1	80	583	-	7.46E+04	-	5.58%	1.34E+06	Fracture predominately in the fiber direction. Many splinters.
I2	80	990	4.32E+04	8.60E+04	1.51%	4.85%	2.85E+06	
I3	80	1016	4.31E+04	8.14E+04	1.45%	4.78%	2.97E+06	
I4	80	997	4.60E+04	8.40E+04	1.80%	4.88%	2.55E+06	
I5	80	993	4.27E+04	7.97E+04	1.81%	4.97%	2.35E+06	
J1	100	1020	4.80E+04	8.55E+04	1.52%	4.49%	3.17E+06	Some fracture visible in the fiber direction. Many splinters.
J2	100	1126	4.85E+04	8.63E+04	1.63%	5.29%	2.97E+06	
J3	100	1139	4.82E+04	8.32E+04	1.68%	4.90%	2.88E+06	
J4	100	1151	4.59E+04	7.96E+04	2.08%	5.29%	2.21E+06	
J5	100	1334	4.76E+04	7.73E+04	1.98%	5.60%	2.41E+06	

Table 3: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: 1-Direction Statistics

Group		Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Strength (psi)	Ult Strength (psi)	Yield Strain (%)	Ult Strain (%)	Modulus (psi)
A	Average	381	6.18E+04 *	7.90E+04	0.65% *	1.21%	1.01E+07
	St Dev	34	3.45E+03 *	1.40E+04	0.05% *	0.28%	1.50E+06
B	Average	457	-	7.40E+04	-	1.14%	6.50E+06
	St Dev	71	-	7.60E+03	-	0.04%	6.10E+05
C	Average	462	-	8.30E+04	-	1.16%	7.20E+06
	St Dev	52	-	8.00E+03	-	0.03%	8.50E+05
D	Average	557	-	8.00E+04	-	1.25%	6.43E+06
	St Dev	107	-	1.10E+04	-	0.08%	5.76E+06
E	Average	563	-	8.00E+04	-	1.41%	5.76E+06
	St Dev	93	-	6.20E+03	-	0.15%	8.60E+05

Table 4: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: 3-Direction Statistics

Group		Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Strength (psi)	Ult Strength (psi)	Yield Strain (%)	Ult Strain (%)	Modulus (psi)
F	Average	382	2.23E+04 *	7.60E+04	0.36% *	5.36%	1.82E+06
	St Dev	61	5.82E+02 *	4.20E+03	0.52% *	0.83%	6.50E+05
G	Average	682	3.74E+04	7.20E+04	1.26%	4.70%	2.92E+06
	St Dev	29	1.13E+04	9.80E+03	0.13%	0.38%	6.20E+05
H	Average	916	4.46E+04	8.10E+04	1.56%	5.01%	2.87E+06
	St Dev	13	7.67E+03	5.30E+03	0.14%	0.39%	4.90E+05
I	Average	650	4.37E+04 **	8.10E+04	1.65% **	5.01%	2.41E+06
	St Dev	186	1.503E+03 **	4.40E+03	0.19% **	0.33%	6.50E+05
J	Average	1154	4.76E+04	8.20E+04	1.78%	5.12%	2.73E+06
	St Dev	113	1.00E+03	3.90E+03	0.24%	0.43%	4.00E+05

*F3-4 used for average and standard deviation

**I2-5 used for average and standard deviation

Table 5: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: Quasi-Static Tests

Direction	Number	Yield Strength (psi)	Ult Strength (psi)
1	1	-	6.33E+04
1	2	-	4.78E+04
1	3	-	6.47E+04
3	1	-	9.38E+04
3	2	-	9.10E+04

Table 6: Torospherical Shell Composed of IM7/E7T1-2: Quasi-Static Statistics

Direction		Ult Strength (psi)
1	average	5.86E+04
	st dev	9.37E+03
3	average	9.24E+04
	st dev	1.99E+03

Table 7: Variance of the Dynamic Mechanical Properties

Property	1-Direction	3-Direction
Strain Rate	9.0 - 19.1%	1.5 - 16%
Yield Strength	5.60%	2.1 - 30.2%
Ultimate Strength	7.7 - 17.8%	1.7 - 13.7%
Yield Strain	7.30%	9.1 - 13.6%
Ultimate Strain	2.2 - 23.4%	6.5 - 15.4%
Modulus	9.4 - 14.4%	14.7 - 35.8%

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